

THE PERCEPTUAL SIMILARITY OF TONE CLUSTERS: AN EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH TO THE LISTENING OF AVANT-GARDE MUSIC

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the musical tone cluster as a prototypical sound of avant-garde music in the 20th and 21st century. Tone clusters marked a turning point from pitch-related techniques of composing in earlier epochs to the sound-based materials used in avant-garde music. Henry Cowell offered the first theoretical reflection about the structure of clusters with a focus on tone density which relying on the number of tones and the ambitus of the cluster. In this paper we first show the results of a sound discrimination experiment, where participants had to rate the sound similarity of prototypical cluster sounds with varying in densities. The results show congruency between theoretical features of the cluster structure, results of the timbre feature analysis, and perceptual evaluation of stimuli. The correlation between tone cluster density and psychoacoustical roughness was $r = .95$ and between roughness and similarity ratings $r = .74$. Overall, the similarity ratings of cluster sounds can be grouped into two classes of sounds: (a) those clusters with a high grade of perceptual discrimination depending on the cluster density and (b) those clusters of a more aurally saturated structure making it difficult to separate and evaluate them. Additionally, the relationship between similarity ratings and psychoacoustical features was also examined. Our findings can provide valuable insights into aural training methods for avant-garde music.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginnings of avant-garde music in the 20th century, the aspect of “sound” has become the essential issue in compositional techniques. In the early 1910s, the American composer Henry Cowell (1897-1965) founded a new theoretical conception of sound through the exploration of tone clusters. In addition, Cowell developed a basic theory about tone clusters in his book *New Musical Resources* [1]. Tone clusters marked a turning point in music history: they make up chords which are characterized by noisiness in opposite to “tonalness, that describes the hearing-related characteristic how a sound differs from noise.” [2, p. 363] Therefore, the categories of tonal harmony, i. e. consonance and dissonance, became less sufficient for under-

standing harmonic theory. In 1960, György Ligeti captured this idea of tone cluster sounds in his orchestral piece *Atmosphères* prominently employing this innovative compositional technique. This led to the musicological need for the development of a compositional theory about the elements of musical sounds.

It was the aim of this research to get a first impression about the perception of tone clusters as a principal prototype of the modern chord. In earlier research, music with tone clusters was interpreted through graphical analysis of the music score. However, in this study we have considered methods of music psychology that allow us to investigate more precisely the perceptual aspects associated with avant-garde music. In addition to our psychological study, we performed a psychoacoustical feature analysis on the stimulus set.

The dependent variables for cluster evaluation used in this study were *interestingness* [3] and *similarity*. We used the participants’ perception of similarity as our basic psychological concept for listening to music. Our first hypothesis is based on the influence of *tone cluster density*, which describes the relation between the number of individual tones and the overall range of the tone cluster. Figure 1 shows a hypothetical graph of the relation between the rating value of the perception of similarity and tone cluster density under two hypothesized effects. We assumed that the similarity of two tone clusters is characterized by a global maximum distributed around the difference of densities $\Delta D = 0$ (hypothesis A). Otherwise, if density had only a small effect, it would be assumed that the perception of similarity is determined by a saturation effect with increasing density (hypothesis B).

Figure 1. Hypothesized perception of similarity.

The tone clusters' height and range of all stimuli have been fixed in the experimental design to remove their influence on the perception of similarity.

2. THEORY

2.1 Definition

Tone clusters are musical chords formed by three or more adjacent tones that usually come from narrowly spaced intervals: for instance, seconds in twelve tone equal-temperament. However, pieces using microtonal intervals exist as well (e.g., Krzysztof Penderecki's *Anaklasis* uses quarter-tones). The noisiness of a sound is a specific property of tone clusters.

2.2 Cowell's theory of tone clusters

Henry Cowell gave the following definition: "Tone-clusters, then, are chords built from major and minor seconds, which in turn are derived from the upper reaches of the overtone series and have, therefore, a sound foundation." [1, p. 117] Cowell called the grouping of three tones spaced in seconds *cluster-triads*. He compared the chord formation of tone clusters with the harmonic principles of tonal music: Just as there are combinations of major and minor thirds in conventional triads in tonal music, there are combinations of major and minor seconds in cluster-triads (see Figure 2). Larger tone clusters are combinations of these basic elements.

Figure 2. Cowell's example of tone cluster-triads [1, p. 117].

In this way Cowell describes the inner structure of tone-clusters: "These four triads are the basis of all larger clusters, which can have great variety, owing to the many different possible juxtapositions of the triads within larger clusters." [1, p. 118] Cowell also described tone clusters related to the layout of the keyboard. Tone clusters played on the black keys corresponded to the pentatonic scale and those played on the white keys to the diatonic scale. This shows that Cowell's theoretical approach was mostly informed by intuition, although he argues that tone clusters and cluster-triads are related to the higher reaches of the overtone series. In this way, Cowell depicted tone clusters as an inevitable progression in the development of music in history.

2.3 Density of tone clusters

The substantial idea of tone clusters is the combination of a large number of seconds in the chord. Clearly, it becomes impossible to distinguish single pitches or intervals in a tone cluster which is the reason that density is considered as an alternative theoretical explanation. The term "density" was first proposed by Mauricio Kagel as a specification of Cowell's cluster-triads [4].

The density of tone clusters relates to the number of pitches contained in the chord and its ambitus. It is calculated by the equation

$$D = \frac{N-1}{W} \cdot 12 \quad (1)$$

where D is the density, N the quantity of tones, W the width of the tone cluster and 12 is a normalization factor. Unlike its common usage in traditional harmony, octave equivalence is not considered in this theoretical approach. This means that it is necessary to count all registers of the pitches of the chords as well as those in octaves, which are usually ignored (e. g. in A. Fortes "pitch-class set theory", see [5], see also [6]).

3. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

3.1 Stimuli

For this study, we chose ten tone cluster sounds of different densities which have the same ambitus (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Score of the ten stimuli used in the experiment. These bars indicate a tone-cluster ranging over the two notes outlined. A flat over the tone-cluster indicates that all black keys are used, a natural that all white keys are used.

The stimuli were produced by a MIDI-controlled sample library piano sound. The range of all tone clusters was two

octaves or $W = 24$ semi-tones. The pitch range was fixed from C3 to C5 (181.1 to 523.3 Hz). All stimuli had a duration of 3.5 s. One of the ten tone clusters was chosen as a reference sound. This reference chord can be described as a combination of tones based on the diatonic scale. This cluster can be regarded as prototypical and is found in Cowell's piano works, for example. The cluster density of the reference item has a mean value of $D_{REF} = 7.0$ tones per octave.

The other items were designed to represent various grades of density from 3.5 to 12.0 (tones per octave, see Table 1).

Cluster	Density D	Number of tones N
REF	7.0	15
VC1	3.5	8
VC2	5.0	11
VC3	6.0	13
VC4	6.5	14
VC5	7.0	15
VC6	8.5	18
VC7	9.5	20
VC8	10.5	22
VC9	12.0	25

Table 1. Densities and the number of tones from the cluster stimuli REF and VC1-VC9.

Some chords are typically used in works with tone clusters: Item VC2 is based on the pentatonic scale and item VC3 on the whole tone scale. Item VC5 is a combination of two different diatonic tone clusters that are non-equivalent in both octaves. The tone cluster items VC6-VC8 were constructed with intervallic structures which were composed arbitrarily. For these chords with densities between 8.0 and 10.5 there are no specific references within music theory literature. Thus, these items completed the selection of stimuli with those grades of density which were not represented through the other tone cluster stimuli.

3.2 Participants

3.2.1 Demographic Data

$N = 50$ students of the Hanover University of Music, Drama and Media (26 female) took part in the experiment. The mean age was $M = 21.9$ years, $SD = 2.6$ (range between 19 and 29 years).

3.2.2 Musical experience

The participants were students in music performance, music education or musicology. The students had been studying for varying durations of between 1 and 15 semesters. Most of them played one or more instruments (16 pianists, 11 singers, 10 guitarists or string players. Additional instruments were percussion, trumpet, flute or saxophone). As a control variable, the degree of "musical sophistication" of the participants was determined by the German version of the Goldsmiths Musical Sophistication Index

[7]. The inventory's "general factor" (18 items) and "musical training" (1 additional item) were applied. Participants were asked to indicate their degree of agreement for each statement on a seven-point Likert scale. They completed the questionnaire before the auditory experiment.

3.3 Design and Procedure

There were two dependent variables in the experimental design of this study: *interestingness* and *similarity* of each sound when compared to the reference cluster. The experiment was divided into two parts. The operationalization of the experiment was supported by a customized version of the STEP software package [8]. The two computer displays that were visible to the participants during the experiment are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

In the first part, the participants were asked to rate the ten tone clusters. The following instruction was given: "Please rate the ten sounds 'A' to 'J' on a scale from 0 'very uninteresting' to 100 'very interesting'" (see Figure 4). In this phase of the experiment, the participants were not informed about the reference cluster. Participants could repeatedly listen to the sounds and compare them directly. This procedure also served to familiarize participants with the stimuli.

The second part of the experiment was an adaption of the Multi Stimulus with Hidden Reference and Anchor (MUSHRA) paradigm, reported in a recommendation of the International Telecommunication Union [9]. In this design, the reference tone cluster REF is used as an anchor. Participants were asked to compare the reference item with each of the other nine stimuli (VC1 to VC9). The presented stimuli were computer-controlled with difference randomization for each participant. The participants did not know which tone cluster was being presented. The panel displayed the following instruction: "Please rate the similarity between sound 'A' and sound 'REF' on a scale from 0 'maximally dissimilar' to 100 'maximally similar'" (see Figure 5).

Figure 4. Panel from the first part (interestingness rating): simultaneous presentation of the ten stimuli.

Figure 5. Panel of the second part (similarity rating): pairwise comparison with the reference stimulus.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Musical sophistication index of participants

The mean Gold-MSI general factor score of the sample was $M = 99.1$ [75, 112], $SD = 8.5$. The maximum possible score of the general factor was 127. This means that the participants were highly experienced in the field of music and can be regarded as experts. The special factor “musical training” gave a mean score of $M = 38.5$ [29, 46], $SD = 4.1$ and $Max = 49$. Participants estimated their experience in music theory with $M = 4.0$ ($SD = 1.8$). The high degree of sophistication in our sample is the precondition for a high reliability of ratings.

4.2 Interestingness of tone cluster

4.2.1 Interestingness ratings

The interestingness ratings were higher for the items REF and VC1-VC3 compared to the other sounds (VC4-VC9). Overall, we observed a descending trend in perceived interestingness. Table 2 displays the mean ratings in Part 1 of the experiment.

Cluster	Density	Interestingness	95% CI	
			LL	UL
	[3.5, 12.0]	M		
VC1	3.5	75.5	70.1	80.9
VC2	5.0	62.7	56.3	69.1
VC3	6.0	70.7	62.6	78.8
VC4	6.5	50.3	45.5	55.1
VC5	7.0	43.6	37.4	49.8
REF	7.0	61.5	54.0	69.0
VC6	8.5	43.1	35.5	50.7
VC7	9.5	40.2	32.1	48.3
VC8	10.5	46.2	38.9	53.5
VC9	12.0	43.0	34.8	51.2

Table 2. Average ratings of interestingness (M) with 95 % CI (LL = lower limit, UL = upper limit).

Figure 6 displays the average ratings of interestingness with 95% confidential intervals (CI). As a fitting curve, a polynomial regression line was calculated (high strength of association $R^2 = .75$).

Figure 6. Average ratings of interestingness (with 95% CIs and regression line).

4.2.2 Factor analysis performed with the interestingness ratings data set

A factor analysis (varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization) was conducted to reduce the complexity of interestingness ratings. Two main components with an eigenvalue > 1 were found, explaining 67% of variance. The factor loadings are shown in Table 3. Due to their exploratory nature, the results of the factor analyses and their possible meanings will be investigated in the discussion.

Cluster	Density	Components	
		1	2
	[3.5, 12.0]		
REF	7.0		.757
VC1	3.5		.741
VC2	5.0		.709
VC3	6.0		.527
VC4	6.5	.834	
VC5	7.0	.837	
VC6	8.5	.852	
VC7	9.5	.881	
VC8	10.5	.914	
VC9	12.0	.910	
Eigenvalues		4.83	2.08

Table 3. Factor loadings of the interestingness ratings.¹

4.3 Tone cluster similarity ratings

4.3.1 Recognition of the Hidden Reference

The mean overall similarity rating of the hidden reference to itself was $M = 96.4$ (95% CI [99.1, 93.7]) and was therefore very high and consistent among participants. In other words, participants rated the hidden reference when compared to the reference as nearly identical, which shows a high judgement reliability of the participants. Significant differences of means between the reference item to the other items were found. A t-test confirmed this relevant result ($t(49) = 21.82, p < .001, d = 3.09$). Only four participants rated the similarity of the hidden reference to the given reference with a value < 90 . However, we decided to keep these subjects in the statistical analysis. Because of the strong recognition effect, we excluded the hidden reference in further analysis of the tone cluster density effect on the perception of similarity.

4.3.2 Similarity Ratings

Table 4 displays the similarity ratings we found for the tone clusters VC1-VC9.

Cluster	Density	Similarity Rating	95% CI	
			<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>
	[3.5, 12.0]	<i>M</i>		
VC1	3.5	25.64	19.8	31.5
VC2	5.0	35.64	28.6	42.9
VC3	6.0	43.64	37.0	50.3
VC4	6.5	44.38	37.7	51.0
VC5	7.0	56.06	49.3	62.8
VC6	8.5	54.92	48.2	61.6
VC7	9.5	45.70	39.2	52.2
VC8	10.5	47.54	41.1	54.0
VC9	12.0	50.30	43.5	57.1

Table 4. Average similarity ratings (*M*) with 95 % CI (*LL* = lower limit, *UL* = upper limit).

The distribution of the average similarity ratings might be represented as a bimodal distribution with the maxima near the density values of 7 and 12 tones per octave. The mean ratings of the items VC7-VC9 were similar. A polynomial curve fit is plotted in Figure 7 below (strength of association $R^2 = .91$).

Figure 7. Average ratings of similarity (with 95% CIs and regression line).

4.3.3 Factor analysis performed on the similarity ratings

The performance of a factor analysis (varimax rotation with Kaiser normalization) with the similarity ratings revealed a 3-factor solution (see Table 5). Three main components with an eigenvalue > 1 were found, explaining 63% of the variance.

¹ All values with $r < .5$ were suspended in this table.

Cluster	Density	Components		
		1	2	3
	[3.5, 12.0]			
VC7	9.5	.739		
VC5	7.0	.714		
VC1	3.5	.642		
VC9	12.0	.592		
VC3	6.0		.752	
VC2	5.0		.750	
VC8	10.5		.673	
VC4	6.5			.822
VC6	8.5			.756
	Eigenvalues	2.06	1.98	1.67

Table 5. Factor loadings of the similarity ratings.²

4.4 Psychoacoustical measures

4.4.1 Roughness

In a last step of stimulus analysis, the psychoacoustical roughness of the 10 cluster sounds was calculated. Roughness is a psychoacoustical feature which determines the tone cluster's degree of noisiness. A timbre feature analysis is in line with the recommendations for perceptual evaluation of sounds as suggested by Fastl and Zwicker [2]. It was performed with the software *dBsonic* [10] (see Table 6).

Cluster	Density	Roughness
	[3.5, 12.0]	<i>M</i> [centi Asper (cA)]
REF	7.0	17.81
VC01	3.5	15.79
VC02	5.0	16.57
VC03	6.0	17.30
VC04	6.5	19.58
VC05	7.0	20.13
VC06	8.5	20.13
VC07	9.5	21.28
VC08	10.5	22.47
VC09	12.0	22.96

Table 6. Psychoacoustical roughness values of stimuli.

The correlation between the theoretical values of the tone cluster density and psychoacoustical roughness was $r = .95$. The correlation between roughness and similarity ratings was $r = .74$. This calculation excluded the hidden reference REF.

4.4.2 Mel-Frequency-Cepstral-Coefficient

Another feature for sound and timbre analysis as recommended by Tzanetakis & Cook [11] is the Mel-Frequency-Cepstral-Coefficient (MFCC). MFCCs have been used in

speech analysis and have also been established for musical sound identification (see Loughran et al. [12]). Based on the perceptually based Mel scale, MFCCs can be used to reduce the complexity of spectral information by identification of coefficients which can be correlated with experimental data. The MFCC analysis was based on the MIR-Toolbox [13]. The MFCC0 is a feature which represents the average energy of the samples. The tone cluster density and the MFCC0 correlated by $r = .98$ (see Table 7). The correlation between the MFCC0 and similarity ratings (except the hidden reference) was $r = .79$. Tzanetakis and Cook recommend the MFCCs 2 to 6 for musical genre classification. Table 7 also displays the MFCCs 0 and 2 to 7. The correlation between the MFCCs and cluster density values of the stimuli can be seen in Table 8. This table also displays that the MFCCs correlated with the similarity ratings. The highest correlations were found between the MFCC 2, MFCC 6 and MFCC 7 and measures displayed in the columns, i. e. density, similarity and roughness.

Cluster	Density	MFCC			
		0	2	3	4
REF	7.0	5.444	-.250	.992	.020
VC01	3.5	4.367	-.089	1.088	.080
VC02	5.0	4.890	-.226	1.019	.040
VC03	6.0	5.439	-.164	1.033	.058
VC04	6.5	5.596	-.179	1.122	.181
VC05	7.0	5.656	-.243	1.053	.121
VC06	8.5	6.195	-.208	.990	.099
VC07	9.5	6.289	-.241	1.114	.159
VC08	10.5	6.439	-.235	1.061	.083
VC09	12.0	6.750	-.231	1.053	.106

Cluster	Density	MFCC		
		5	6	7
REF	7.0	.360	.113	.147
VC01	3.5	.359	-.110	.018
VC02	5.0	.347	.058	.035
VC03	6.0	.398	-.031	.085
VC04	6.5	.403	.115	.040
VC05	7.0	.329	.017	.093
VC06	8.5	.424	.066	.134
VC07	9.5	.374	.141	.101
VC08	10.5	.367	.105	.192
VC09	12.0	.374	.116	.172

Table 7. Values of the MFCC performance.

² All values with $r < .59$ were suspended in this table.

MFCC	Correlation coefficients		
	<i>r</i>		
	with density	with similarity ratings (except REF)	with roughness
MFCC2	-.63	-.73	-.59
MFCC3	.02	-.29	.21
MFCC4	.29	.35	.51
MFCC5	.18	.21	.14
MFCC6	.71	.56	.68
MFCC7	.86	.68	.75

Table 8. Correlation between selected MFCCs, cluster density, and similarity ratings.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results from the factor analysis interestingness ratings may be interpreted as a confirmation of the expectation that familiarity of clusters is important in this kind of perception. The first factor can be characterized by unfamiliar cluster structures. The second factor included these chords which can be described with well-known concepts in music theory such as pentatonic or diatonic: for example, the item VC1 is a type of chord that can be found in jazz. It can be surmised that listeners are more familiar with the sound of such types of chords.

The results of the similarity rating experiment can be interpreted as a confirmation of the ability of the participants to grasp the specific quality of tone clusters. This can be observed in the high recognition rate of the hidden reference cluster in the similarity rating. Considering the theoretical background, we expected a unimodal distribution of the ratings with a maximum at the density value of the reference item. However, what we found via statistical analysis (see Figure 7) seemed to be a bimodal distribution of similarity ratings. The first peak of the regression line is positioned near the tone cluster density of 7.0 tones per octave. The second maximum is represented by the Cluster VC9 with a density of 12. This result suggests that a saturation effect in the aural perception of cluster sounds should be considered. The psychoacoustical timbre features and the theoretical tone cluster densities were highly correlated. The measure of density can be used to describe the strength of structure. This can also be seen in the correlation of psychoacoustical measures and similarity ratings. However, the factor analysis revealed further aspects to be examined in future studies.

Our findings can provide the basis for a systematic ear training for avant-garde music sounds. The insight into the density effect of tone clusters can be used not only for analysis of cluster sound music. It can also be an approach to a perceptual theory of timbre-based avant-garde music. Future research will focus on slightly noticeable differences between tone cluster structures.

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